

Dynamics of the Chemical Composition of Precipitation and Input of Elements in an Agricultural Area in Southern Bulgaria

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Abstract

The study of the chemical composition of precipitation is an important factor in determining the input of elements and the total anthropogenic load in agroecosystems. The study presents the results of a 4-year monitoring of the chemical composition of precipitation from the area of the experimental field Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv on Alluvial-meadow soil (Fluvisol). The effects of chemical elements imported with the atmospheric deposition on vulnerable soils in an intensive agricultural practice were evaluated. The data showed that the investigated precipitations are characterized by a slightly acidic to neutral reaction. A significant seasonal and annual variation of the elements in them was observed, with a higher coefficient of variation reported for cations and nitrogen (61-68%). As a result of the conducted research, the following order of change in the concentrations of cations - $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$ and of anions - $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^- \text{N}$ in precipitation was established. The significant correlation found between Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ($r=0.92; 0.97$) and the weak one between NH_4^+ , $\text{NO}_3^- \text{N}$ and SO_4^{2-} suggest a buffer factor against precipitation acidity, and anions concentrations did not represent a risk for a direct negative impact on the soil and the crops grown in the area.

Keywords: rainfall, cations, anions, dynamics, agroecosystems

Introduction

Agricultural production is most affected by climatic conditions and their changes. In recent decades, a significant increase in hydrological extreme events in Europe is seen, which have a significant impact on various aspects of socio-economic life and agro-ecosystems. The extreme climate events are difficult to assess due to their high degree of variability and limited duration of observations (Huo et al., 2020). Rainfall in recent years are considered as an important factor for realizing the productive potential of the soil. Moreover they are significant item of revenue in the balance of the elements in the agroecosystems and represents a way to determining critical loads. The problem of the chemical composition of precipitation is significant, as they effect on the entire ecosystem - soil, plants, waters. According to the studies of certain authors the seasonal fluctuations in temperature and intensive precipitations are the reason for significant losses of nitrate (Mitchell, 2011). The chemical composition of precipitations is the result of climatic conditions, natural

processes and human activities and reflects the characteristics and state of atmospheric pollution (Xing et al., 2017; Zhong et al., 2022). Determining the background state of the atmosphere is becoming increasingly difficult as much of the continent is subject to anthropogenic impacts of local, regional or transboundary origin. According from character and the strength of these impacts, changes occur in the physical- chemical composition and properties of atmospheric sediments. Conducted research Gauger et al., (2001) shows that precipitation contain and transfer chemical elements which in most cases have anthropogenic origin and are defined as pollutants with negative impacts on the ecosystems in which they are deposited and accumulated. Furthermore, passing through the soil the precipitations are filtered and dissolved the elements contained there in, where they can have a significant impact on the quality of groundwater. On the other hand, however, in surface waters (rivers, lakes, etc.), a large part of these elements are undesirable as they cause eutrophication. It is also possible that many plant communities are not able to process into biomass the amounts of nitrogen that come with precipitation, which then enters the surface runoff. Studies Yang et al., (2016) found that even if applied agricultural techniques and fertilization rates are at a high level, wheat and maize yields are also significantly affected by the amount of rainfall. That is why, according to researchers, it is necessary a comprehensive assessment of the role of precipitation and its impact on the entire system is needed (Gornall et al., 2010).

The purpose of the study was to assess the dynamics of the content of chemical elements in the precipitation from the area of the Tsalapitsa experimental field for the period 2020-2023.

Materials and Methods

The researched area is located at the experimental field of ISSAPP "N.Pushkarov" in the village of Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region, South Bulgaria (24⁰35'E; 42⁰14'N and 180 m above the sea-level). The chemical composition of precipitation and atmospheric depositions was determined after measuring their volume collected with standard rain gauges (Gyurova and Peev, 1981) after every registered rainfall. Depending on the volume of water and the concentrations of chemical elements their revenue were calculated. Due to the random character in the distribution of precipitation (quantity, frequency and intensity), the chemical composition of individual precipitation was investigated, after which they were averaged and presented with their average monthly values. Regardless of the significant variation in the data, the four-year observations allow obtaining representative average characteristics for the chemical composition of precipitation. The pH values and chemical composition (NO₃⁻N, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, HCO₃⁻, Cl⁻, SO₄⁻,) of precipitation are determined using the following methods: pH – potentiometrically (Arinushkina, 1970), potassium and sodium were determined by flame photometer, calcium and magnesium – by atomic absorption spectrometry – AAS (Page et al., 1982), nitrogen content, chlorides and sulfates were measured by „Spectroquant Pharo 100”, hydrocarbonate by titration with 0.02nH₂SO₄ to pH 4.4 (Arinushkina, 1970). The climate in the area is hot with dry summers and mild winters and irregularly rainfall distribution (Levicharska, 1991). The site is characterized by an average annual rainfall of 447 mm for 2020, 601 mm - 2021, 410 mm - 2022 and 150 mm for 2023, which are summarized up to June. The period accepted as a norm 1961-1990 has an amount of precipitation of 492 mm. The average annual air temperature is 12.5-12.8 °C, in July – 23.4, in January it is around zero degrees. In the study area, the soil is Alluvial-meadow (Eutric Fluvisol), (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) This type of soil is used for intensive agriculture and is therefore it is suitable for the purposes of the study. The soil profile has a coarse texture, low water holding capacity and fairly high water permeability, which creates conditions for active migration of chemical elements along the profile. The arable horizon has the following mean characteristics: light texture, low clay content (18.6%),

bulk density between 1.54 and 1.66 g.cm⁻³, slightly acidic reaction pH_{H2O} (6.0), total nitrogen (0.052 %), humus content - 1.23%, and cation exchange capacity – 22.4 cmol.100 g⁻¹ (Stoichev, 1997).

Results and Discussion

The average monthly amounts of precipitation do not affect the values of the investigated parameters that much, but they are extremely important for the development of the cultivated crop and the storage of moisture in the soil. From the obtained data it is established autumn-spring maximum of precipitation, which is generally characteristic for this climatic region. A drought was observed in the summer of 2021 and significantly the amount of precipitation for the month of October - 165 mm (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Amount of precipitation (mm) for the studied period from the experimental field of Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv and the period accepted as the norm 1961-1990.

In the same year, the largest amount of precipitation was measured - 601 mm, while in 2020 and 2022 they are with similar values, around 410 - 450 mm and approaching the period accepted as the norm. The lowest amount was reported in 2023, at 150 mm, but the measured precipitation was until June. However, compared to other years, the values for the six months for 2023 are about 1.5 - 2 times lower. It was found that the largest amount of precipitation was in the month of April - 88 mm in 2020, while in 2022, the largest volume was measured in the month of June - 94 mm

From the Figure 2, which shows the number of days with precipitation in the respective months for the studied period, it is found that in the spring months - April, May, June, the most days with precipitation were reported.

The data show that the precipitation in the study area (Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region) is characterized by a slightly acidic to close to neutral reaction. During the studied periods, precipitation with an acidic or alkaline reaction was not detected. Some researchers Lara et al., (2010) in their studies reported that the content of calcium ions in the form of CaCO₃ neutralizes the acid components in precipitation. It is possible that the acid potential of precipitation at such a pH is insignificant compared to the neutralizing capacity of soils. It was established that throughout the studied period 2020-2023, the pH values were in the range of 6.5 to 6.8 (Table 1).

Figure 2. Number of days with precipitation for the study period 2020-2023

The lowest values reported were in 2020 (Figure 3). It is interesting to note that during the spring months a lower pH values were recorded, while during the summer period the pH values were closer to neutral, i.e. fluctuations in spring are more significant in the slightly acidic zone. This observation is more pronounced in 2020 and 2022. In their research Małeckı et al., (2022), have observed the tendency to reduce the acidity of precipitation and improve the quality of its chemical indicators in different parts of Europe which is associated with a transition to more sustainable economies. In a similar study, the authors Keresztesi et al., (2019), found a homogeneous distribution of the analyzed chemical series, which they associated with the implementation of a single European policy in the area of environmental protection.

Figure 3. pH values of precipitation in the experimental field of Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region, during the period (2020-2023).

The results presented in the Table 1 and Figure 4 show that during the studied period 2020-2023, the average content of potassium in precipitation varies from (1.81 ± 0.77) to (2.56 ± 1.69) , and sodium from 0.81 to 1.25 mg.l^{-1} , no significant change of the average content of these two ions in precipitation compared to previous periods of the studied area was found. It is believed that their

presence is mainly connected with soil dust and that values of about 0.5-0.6 to 3.0 - 3.5 mg.l⁻¹ are considered background.

Figure 4. Dynamics of potassium, sodium, calcium and magnesium in precipitation in the experimental field of Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region, during the period (2020-2023).

The data show that the content of divalent cations in precipitation is higher in the spring and summer months of 2020, where calcium values reach 15 mg.l⁻¹, (average 8.65 ± 4.06), and the lowest in 2023 of 1.93 mg.l⁻¹, (average 5.61 ± 2.93). It is possible that greater dusting is the reason for their concentration in the precipitation. The content of magnesium is about 2.5-3 times lower compared to that of calcium (1.72 - 2.64 mg.l⁻¹). However, it has been observed greater variation in its values was observed (Table 1).

The concentration of ammonia nitrogen in 2020, ranges from 1,95 to 6,60 mg.l⁻¹, while the reported amount of nitrate nitrogen is in the range from 0.73 to 10.90 mg.l⁻¹. The nitrogen content was found to be highest in the spring of the same year, a situation similar to that of calcium and magnesium. As it is shown on Figure 5 ammonia nitrogen concentration in 2021 varies from 2,29 to 6,92 (average $3,83 \pm 1,58$), while for nitrate nitrogen the mean concentrations were 3.26 ± 0.64 . The lowest measured average values of nitrogen were in 2023.

Figure 5. Dynamics of nitrogen content in precipitation in the experimental field of Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region, during the period (2020-2023).

The results for the content of hydrocarbonates and chlorine in the precipitation show insignificant differences compared to earlier study periods in the area of Tsalapitsa. The concentrations of hydrocarbonates in precipitation for the studied period ranged from 25.37 to 28.09 mg.l⁻¹ with a low coefficient of variation (Table 1). The average values for chlorine are from 4.16 to 5.29 mg.l⁻¹, as the chlorine content is 5-6 times lower compared to that of hydrocarbonates (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Dynamics of hydrocarbonates, chlorides and sulfates content in precipitation in the experimental field of Tsalapitsa, Plovdiv region, during the period (2020-2023).

The chemical composition of precipitation shows significant seasonal and yearly trends. The table shows that the dominant ions are Ca²⁺, NH₄⁺, SO₄²⁻ and HCO₃⁻. In a similar study, Hontoria, et al., 2003 found that the predominant cations were those of calcium and that they were the main neutralizing agent of nitrates and sulfates, the authors associate this with the stronger influence of the soil in the composition of the precipitation, in contrast to that of the marine influence.

The established significant correlation between Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ (r=0.92 - 0.97) and the weak one between NH₄⁺ and NO₃⁻ (r=0.15 - 0.22), as well as between NH₄⁺ and SO₄²⁻, (r=0.19) suggest a buffer factor against precipitation acidity.

To assess the impact of atmospheric deposition upon the soil it is important to determine the total amount of the ions which included in the annual precipitation. The revenue input of the chemical elements in the precipitation is calculated on the basis an average chemical composition and the total annual rainfall (410 - 600 mm) in the region of Tsalapitsa. From the obtained data, it is established that the input of calcium is from 34.3 to 40.6 kg.ha⁻¹, of magnesium 7.6 - 15.2 kg.ha⁻¹, with ammonia nitrogen it is within the limits of 10.7 - 20.3 kg.ha⁻¹, and with nitrate nitrogen 14.1 - 22.7 kg.ha⁻¹ (Figure 7). According to Malecki et al., (2022) there has been an increasing trend of air quality improvement in recent years. This trend is also observed in the measured ion concentrations and reduced wet deposition loads of the containing acid-forming compounds. The neutralizing capacity of rainwater is increased by the NH₄⁺ it contains, indicating that some of the neutralization takes place in the lower atmosphere. It was found that the average annual input of nitrogen with precipitation for the Tsalapitsa region in previous studies over a 30-year period is about 20 - 23 kg.ha⁻¹.

Table 1. Chemical composition of precipitation for the period 2020-2023 from the area of the Tsalapitsa.

		Chemical elements, mg.l ⁻¹								
2020	pH	K ⁺	Na ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	NH ₄ -N	NO ₃ -N	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻
min	5,9	0,24	0,58	2,74	0,29	1,95	0,73	17,26	2,9	14,8
max	6,95	5,73	2,02	15	3,55	6,6	10,9	32,87	8,1	68,4
mean±		2,36±	1,12±	8,65±	1,72±	4,12±	5,09±	25,61±	5,05±	32,31±
Stdv	6,5±0,31	1,37	0,43	4,06	1,17	1,59	3,15	5,17	1,83	18,21
cv	5	58	39	47	68	38	61	20	36	56
2021										
min	6,3	1,4	0,24	4,6	0,5	2,29	1,92	19,52	2,28	12
max	7,3	5,57	1,4	9,73	4,95	6,92	4,25	30,87	7,6	65,66
mean±	6,8±	2,56±	0,82±	6,8±	2,64±	3,83±	3,26±	25,376±	5,29±	33,88±
Stdv	0,33	1,69	0,34	1,67	1,32	1,58	0,64	4,36	1,68	20,11
cv	5	67	41	24	50	41	19	17	32	59
2022										
min	6,35	0,62	0,25	3,81	0,35	0,18	0,37	18,51	0,2	10,6
max	7,3	3,24	2,47	12,4	3,54	4,06	5,18	42,35	7,2	57,34
mean±	6,8±	1,81±	1,25±	8,38±	2,23±	2,63±	3,44±	28,09±	4,4±	36,92±
Stdv	0,24	0,77	0,68	2,76	1,1	1,06	1,32	7,95	2,08	14,04
cv	3	42	54	33	49	40	38	28	47	38
2023										
min	6,2	0,31	0,33	1,93	0,1	1,41	1,48	15,42	2,50	23
max	7,10	2,39	1,09	6,78	4,25	3,15	4,47	38,03	5,80	41
mean±	6,75±	1,27±	0,67±	5,28±	2,08±	2,55±	2,87±	25,88±	3,73±	31,56±
Stdv	0,35	0,93	0,35	3,03	1,43	0,63	1,05	7,88	1,31	7,20
cv	5	58	53	52	68	25	36	29	35	22

Figure 7. Input of chemical elements (kg.ha⁻¹) with precipitation for the studied period

Conclusions

The chemical composition of precipitation shows significant seasonal and annual dynamics and significant variation the data for potassium, magnesium and nitrate nitrogen. As a result of the conducted research, the following descending order of the concentrations of the cations in the precipitation was established: $\text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{NH}_4^+ > \text{Mg}_2^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+$ and the anions: $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{HCO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^-$ N respectively. It was found that among the cations, those of calcium and magnesium prevail, followed by ammonium cations, while among the anions, sulfates are followed by hydrocarbonates, and those of nitrate nitrogen are the lowest. Regarding the pH values and the content of chemical elements for 2020 - 2023, it is found that they do not differ significantly from previous periods studied and their concentration does not represent a risk for a direct negative impact on the soil and the crops grown in the area.

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